

The organizational life cycle of a company

Like human beings, companies have a life cycle and go through different stages of development having a beginning and an end.

According to [Aj Ginsburg](#), The various stages that a company goes through in its development vary according to each particular case. The duration and how they develop in each phase is variable. The management of the employer or the leader in charge is to try to prolong its existence as far as possible, although for many the idea of turning it into an immortal company is an ideal that is sought to be achieved.

There are several stages that a company can go through. Here we will address the most important and how to carry each of them in the best way:

Birth: after analyzing ideas on which business to start, define the name of the company, evaluate budgets, among others, it is decided to start operations.

As Aj Ginsburg states, this stage is characterized by having centralized decisions in the creator and / or founder since the company has a small structure and often with rudimentary processes. The objective is to find a space in the market and be able to generate sales to sustain the business.

Some businesses have their own financing, but a large percentage seek bank financing. It is at this stage where many companies fail to continue their development due to multiple factors such as: lack of market research, poor distribution of capital, centralization of decision making in a single person, etc.

So that the rapid or early death of the company does not occur, Aj Ginsburg recommends in [his publications](#), that the entrepreneur must keep costs under control. If you have few clients, they must be very satisfied taking advantage of personalization or the most personalized service, detecting where the competitive advantage is that can be based to face the next stage.

Growth: the company has a sustained development, it becomes known in the market, revenue grows and customers increase and loyalty, products and / or services are improved, points of sale increase, processes are systematized and there is a professionalization in its development.

In internal management decisions are no longer taken only by the founder. This delegates responsibilities and processes are improved, which acquire a formal character within the organization, so it seeks to incorporate trained external personnel, technicians and professionals who contribute to the improvement of the company.

As Aj Ginsburg argues, at this stage the structure is expanded from a more stable and professional base, with the application of more developed internal policies. This change additionally generates other financing needs, in order to develop and / or implement the business.

Maturity: finally the company has successfully overcome all the obstacles posed by the start of a company. Sales continue to grow and there is an optimal size in the market. Here the objective is to achieve the highest cost and process efficiency possible. Products are improved by generating added value, margins, services are taken care of. The attention to the public is essential for the consolidation of the image. It works hand in hand with technology to create value in customers and tries to keep them loyal and keep attracting new ones.

It cooperates with other companies to launch new projects, many of which require a lot of initial investment or a strong research and development component.

With the consolidated business, new ideas, mostly external, will be sought through mergers and / or acquisitions of the competition. Aj Ginsburg points out [in his academia papers](#), that at this stage the plans to grow are smaller, so it is no longer so aggressive and a rather defensive strategy is adopted.

Death of the company: it can occur at any stage, either at the beginning or when it is growing or at maturity. According to Aj Ginsburg , this is because the company makes mistakes in adapting to the market by not understanding the behavior of the public to see that it changes and the company does not take any action in this regard. Technology is a key factor and those companies that cannot make investments in research and development are destined to fail. Likewise, an organization that does not change, does not innovate and / or is very bureaucratic has a higher risk of dying or being liquidated if the right decisions are not taken.